

DESIGN OPTIMIZATION OF CENTRIFUGAL ROTOR OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: A procedure of stress and strength analysis has been proposed for the centrifugal rotor of composite materials of quasi-isotropic laminates. The goal in this study is to maximize the allowable rotating speed, that is, to minimize the run time with the given path length by changing the geometry and selecting the ply angles in quasi-isotropic laminate. The geometric parameters, i.e., the outer radii and the radius of tube hole are the design variables to find. Two dimensional analysis at each cross section with an elliptic tube hole subjected to internal sample pressures as well as the centrifugal body forces has been performed along the height to calculate the stress distribution with the plane stress assumption, and Tsai-Wu failure criterion is used to calculate the strength ratio. The maximum allowable rotating speed can be, then, increased by changing the radii of the outer surface along the height with the maximum strength ratio under the unit value. The optimal number of ply angles maximizing the allowable rotating speed in quasi-isotropic laminates is also found to be the half number of tube hole, and the optimal laminate rotation angle is half of $[\pi/m]$. A $\pi/3$ laminate, for instance, is stronger than a $\pi/4$ laminate for the centrifugal rotor of 6 tube hole number even though they have the same stiffness. The number of tube hole can be also optimally determined to maximize the sample volume and the allowable rotating speed as well.

KEYWORDS: centrifugal rotor, composite materials, optimum design

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of centrifuges is to separate samples containing sub-cellular and biological particles of different densities from each other by spinning the rotor containing the samples and exerting the centrifugal force on the samples in solution [1, 2]. Existing centrifuges and rotors have, however, several limitations. The majority of existing centrifuge rotors are manufactured from aluminum or titanium alloys, and their use imposes constraints in the design of the centrifuge. For instance, the lifetime of a metal rotor is limited by metal fatigue and corrosion, which restricts the number of runs at maximum speed. Additionally, enough torque must be generated to accelerate a heavy metal rotor to high speeds in reasonably short times. These factors make existing centrifuges large and heavy for the task that they perform.

The application of composite materials to centrifugation has alleviated these problems and opened up new market opportunities. Composite materials are used to reduce the weight of rotors, or to increase sample capacity and rotor efficiency, which are mostly due to their high

specific strengths and abilities of changing ply orientations. For the composite laminated rotor, the quasi-isotropic laminates are mostly used to give the structurally isotropic behavior.

In order to optimize the composite centrifuge, stresses developed in the rotor must be calculated and then reduced as much as possible by changing the geometry and selecting the proper composite materials and ply orientations. In the past, an analytic solution and finite element methods have been used to calculate the stresses of the rotor [3-5]. The general procedures of selecting the dimensions and ply orientations of a composite centrifugal rotor are, however, not presented so far.

In this study, a structural analysis of quasi-isotropic laminated composite rotor has been performed considering the geometric parameters, i.e., the number of holes, the radii of holes, the radial diameter of the rotor and the side angle of slope. All the variables are non-dimensionalized in the governing equations, boundary conditions and material constitutive equations. A strength analysis is then performed to choose the ply orientation of quasi-isotropic laminates to maximize the rotating speed.

STRESS AND STRENGTH ANALYSIS

The composite centrifugal rotor considered in this study is a fixed angle rotor with a tube angle α_0 from the axis of rotation as shown in Figure 1. The rotor can centrifuge up to $2n$ tubes located with equal spatial angles. This rotor develops centrifugal forces for the differential separation of particles. The rotor is thus subjected to both the centrifugal body forces inside the materials and the hydraulic pressures on the cavity surface due to the samples. For the design point of view, it is usually required that the rotor sustain the higher rotation speed with a larger sample volume. For that purpose, the rotor is preferably made of composite materials which have the high specific strengths. The plies are parallel to the x-y plane, and a quasi-isotropic $[\pi/m]$ laminate sequence is used with a laminate rotation angle β as shown in Figure 2. The ply angle m for the given number of tubes $2n$ has an effect on reducing the strength ratios in the materials ($m, n = 3, 4, 5, \dots$), that is, increasing the maximum allowable rotating speed ω .

STRESS ANALYSIS

The stress analysis is based on a plain stress assumption ignoring the z-directional stresses, and the stress distribution for a section parallel to the x-y plane is thus calculated. The stress distributions are thus governed by the radial and circumferential equilibrium equations which are written in cylindrical coordinates as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta}{r} + \rho_c r \omega^2 &= 0 \\ \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}}{r} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where σ_r , σ_θ and $\tau_{r\theta}$ are the radial, circumferential and shear stresses, respectively, and ρ_c denotes the density of composite materials, ω the rotational angular velocity. The length and stress are non-dimensionalized by the radius of the top plane r_0 and $\rho_c r_0^2 \omega$, respectively, and Equation (1) can be then rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_r^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\sigma_r^* - \sigma_\theta^*}{r^*} + r^* &= 0 \\ \frac{1}{r^*} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta^*}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^*}{\partial r^*} + \frac{2\tau_{r\theta}^*}{r^*} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The superscript * thus denotes non-dimension. Since the geometry is repeatedly symmetric, only one portion is analyzed with the symmetry conditions as shown in Figure 1. The maximum radius r_{max}^* of the semi-axes of the elliptic tube hole is determined for the geometry of the given number of tube hole $2n$ and the tube angle α_o :

$$r_{max}^* = \frac{\tan \theta_n}{\tan \theta_n + \sqrt{\tan^2 \theta_n + \cos^2 \alpha_o}} \quad \text{where } \theta_n = \frac{\pi}{2n} \quad (3)$$

The distance of the tube hole center at the top plane denoted by d_o^* is dependently determined from r_{max}^* , and the distance of the tube hole center d_z^* and the surface radii r_z^* along the height z^* are expressed as a function of z^* :

$$\begin{aligned} d_o^* &= 1 - r_{max}^* \\ d_z^* &= d_o^* + z^* \tan \alpha \\ r_z^* &= 1 + z^* \tan \alpha \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

With the notations defined as in the above, the stress boundary conditions for the portion are described as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r^* = \sigma_{r\theta}^* &= 0 \quad \text{on the outer surfaces} \\ \sigma_{\xi\eta}^* &= 0, \quad \sigma_\xi^* = P^*(r^*) \quad \text{inside of the tube hole} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The normal stress σ_ξ due to the pressure of the sample subjected to the centrifugal forces can be calculated using the equilibrium equation of the sample rotating with an angular velocity ω neglecting the gravitation force ;

$$P(r) = \int \rho_s r \omega^2 dr = \frac{1}{2} \rho_s \omega^2 (r^2 - r_f^2) \quad (6)$$

where ρ_s denotes the density of the sample, and r_f a pressure-free radius. The pressure is again normalized as in Equation 2 and P^* in Equation (5) is obtained ;

$$P^* = \frac{\frac{1}{2} \rho_s (r^2 - r_f^2) \omega^2}{\rho_c r_o^2 \omega^2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\rho_s}{\rho_c} (r^{*2} - r_f^{*2}) \quad (7)$$

For the stress-strain relationship, the equivalent isotropic material properties are used because the laminates are quasi-isotropic.

STRENGTH ANALYSIS

Solving the governing equations with the boundary conditions, the off-axis strains ε_{off} in the global x, y and z coordinates are obtained. The on-axis ply stresses σ_{on} of each ply in $[\pi/m]$ laminate are then calculated using the strain transformation matrix \mathbf{T} and the ply material properties \mathbf{Q}_{on} [6];

$$\sigma_{on} = \mathbf{Q}_{on} \varepsilon_{on} = \mathbf{Q}_{on} \mathbf{T} \varepsilon_{off} \quad (8)$$

where the transformation matrix \mathbf{T} is defined as

$$\mathbf{T} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2 \phi & \sin^2 \phi & \cos \phi \sin \phi \\ \sin^2 \phi & \cos^2 \phi & -\cos \phi \sin \phi \\ -2 \cos \phi \sin \phi & 2 \cos \phi \sin \phi & \cos^2 \phi - \sin^2 \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

In Equation (9), ϕ is a ply angle in the laminate.

The failure of the ply material can then be accessed by using a Failure Criterion; Tsai-Wu quadratic failure criterion has been used [6],

$$\sigma_{on}^T \tilde{\mathbf{F}} \sigma_{on} + \bar{\mathbf{F}} \sigma_{on} R - R^2 = 0 \quad (10)$$

Solving Equation (10) yields a strength ratio R indicating the material failure with a value greater than 1. The strength parameters $\bar{\mathbf{F}}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{F}}$ in Equation (10) are defined in terms of the material strengths :

$$\bar{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'} & \frac{1}{Y} - \frac{1}{Y'} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{XX'} & -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{XX'} \frac{1}{YY'}} & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{1}{XX'} \frac{1}{YY'}} & \frac{1}{YY'} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{S^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where X and X' are the tensile and compressive strengths in the fiber direction, Y and Y' in the matrix direction, and S the shear strength.

Notice that, since the equivalent stiffness is the same for a number of angles m in a quasi-isotropic $[\pi/m]$ laminate, the off-axis strains are not changing. The distributions of the stresses and strength ratios at each ply are, however, changing with a quasi-isotropic laminate angle. The distributions of strength ratios are also dependent upon the laminate rotating angle β ; the lay-up angles of a quasi-isotropic laminate with $m=3$ and β are $[\beta, \pi/3 + \beta, 2\pi/3 + \beta]$ as shown in Figure 2. For the given geometry and loading conditions of the rotor, the optimal m and β can be thus found to minimize the maximum strength ratios in the plies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using finite element methods, the stress analysis is performed on the composite rotor with various geometric values. Most important geometric values to design for the composite rotor are a tube hole radius r_i , radii of outer surfaces r_o and the number of tube holes n for the given radius of the top plane r_o and the fixed tube angle α_o . As shown in the analysis, all the dimensions are normalized by r_o .

The determination of radii of outer surfaces r_z^* along the height is important in reducing the stress distribution. The radii r_z^* along the height are determined to minimize the maximum stresses in each cross section with two conditions; in the first case, the radii r_z^* linearly change along the height making a constant slope angle α which is calculated as 25° , and in the second case, the radii r_z^* arbitrarily change along the height. For numerical calculation, a radius of the top plane r_o , a fixed tube angle α_o and the height are taken as 10 cm, 15° and 12.5 cm, respectively. The radius of the tube hole r_i^* is taken as 0.8 times of r_{max}^* and the number of tube hole $2n$ as 6.

The composite material used for calculation is AS4/PK and their material properties are listed in Table 1. The number of ply angle m in quasi-isotropic laminate is considered as 3 with the laminate rotation angle β zero. It is found that the maximum strength ratios always exist along the boundary. The stresses along the tube hole are thus most critical in designing the rotor. The normal stress σ_ξ^* is given by the pressure of the sample with a pressure-free radius r_f the inner point of the tube hole at the top plane and the shear stress $\sigma_{\xi\eta}^*$ is zero as in Equation (5). The specific density of the sample is considered as a constant value of 1.2. The tangential stress σ_η^* is calculated for three cases, and compared with each other. As the first case, the surface slope angle α is the same as the tube angle α_o given as 15° . For the second case, the constant slope angle α minimizing the maximum strength ratios is calculated as 25° . For the third case, the minimization of the maximum strength ratios is achieved by varying slope angle α , that is, changing the outer surface radii along the height. The stress distributions at the sections of z^* equal to 0.25, 0.75 and 1.25 for each case are shown in Figure 3. It is noticed that the variations of the stresses and the maximum values of the tangential stresses along the boundary line in the last two cases are reduced as compared to those of a case that $\alpha=\alpha_o$. The maximum allowable rotating speeds ω which are corresponding to the maximum strength ratio of unit value are, thus, increased from 31,000 rpm by 20% and 28% for the last two cases.

As a general result for the above case, or changing the ratio of the tube hole radius r_i^* with respect to the r_{max}^* , the distributions of the maximum strength ratio along the height are plotted for the above three cases as shown in Figure 4. From the contour line in Figure 4, the ratio r_i^*/r_{max}^* can be determined without any material failure for the given height z^* . Notice that the larger tube hole can exist for the given height z^* by changing the surface radii along the height as shown in Figure 4.

The maximum allowable rotating speed can be even more increased by properly choosing the number of the ply angles m in quasi-isotropic laminate and the laminate rotation angle β . In order to show the effects of m and β , the variations of maximum allowable rotating speed ω are calculated using Equation (10) and plotted by varying the angle β for four cases of m equal to 3, 4, 5, and 6 at three sections of z^* , and shown in Figure 5. The best value of m is shown as 3 which is equal to n , and the angle β is half of π/m , or 30° , except that at $z^*=1.25$

where the angle β is 6° . The maximum allowable rotating speeds ω are summarized in Table 2.

As a last example, for the constant total tube volume, the maximum rotating speed ω can be also even increased by properly choosing the number of tube hole n and are shown in Figure 6. In this example, the height z^* is taken as 1.0, the number of ply angles m equal to n , the constant angle α equal to α_o as 15° . The total tube volume V_t is normalized by r_o^3 and denoted by V_t^* . For the volume V_t^* equal to 1.2, the best number of tube hole is 3 and for V_t^* equal to 0.8, the number 6.

CONCLUSION

It is shown that the maximum allowable rotating speed of the composite rotor can be increased by changing the outer surface slope angles along the height. The maximum allowable radius of the tube hole for the given number of tube holes is also calculated by minimizing the maximum strength ratios for all the sections. The optimal number of ply angles maximizing the allowable rotating speed in quasi-isotropic laminates is found to be the half number of tube hole, and the optimal laminate rotation angle is half of $[\pi/m]$. The number of tube hole can be also optimally determined to maximize the sample volume and the allowable rotating speed as well.

Figure 1. Geometries and coordinate systems for a fixed angle rotor with a tube angle α_o ; Determination of the maximum length of the semi-axes of the elliptic tube hole for a repeating portion of angle π/n (the top figure)

Figure 2. Geometry of layup sequence of quasi-isotropic laminate in a composite centrifugal rotor; π/m is a ply angle and β is the laminate rotation angle.

Figure 3. Distribution of tangential stresses σ_{η}^* along the boundary line η for the rotor of $r_i^* = 0.8 r_{max}^*$, $m=n=3$, $\alpha_0=15^\circ$, and $r_o=10$ cm.

Distribution of Strength Ratio, R

Figure 4. Distribution of maximum strength ratios R over the height and the tube hole radius r_i^* for the rotor of $m=n=3$, $\alpha_o=15^\circ$, and $r_o=10 \text{ cm}$.

Figure 5. The maximum allowable rotating speed ω versus the laminate rotating angle β when $r_i^* = 0.8 r_{max}^*$, $n=3$, and α =optimized

Figure 6. The maximum allowable rotating speed ω versus the number of tube hole n for the constant tube volume of 1.2 and 0.8 of the rotor of $m=n$, $\beta=0$, and $\alpha^o=\alpha=15^o$

Table 1. Material properties of centrifugal composite rotor for numerical calculation.

Material Properties (AS4/PK)	Values
Longitudinal Young's Modulus, E_x	134 GPa
Transverse Young's Modulus, E_y	8.9 GPa
Shear Modulus, E_s	5.1 GPa
Longitudinal Poisson's Ratio, ν	0.28
Longitudinal Tensile Strength, X	2130 MPa
Longitudinal Compressive Strength, X'	1100 MPa
Transverse Tensile Strength, Y	80 MPa
Transverse Compressive Strength, Y'	200 MPa
Shear Strength, S	160 MPa
Density, ρ_c	1600 Kg/m ³

Table 2. The increase of the maximum allowable rotating speed along the height z^* by varying the outer surface radii r_z^* and laminate rotation angle β ; $n=m=3$ and $\alpha=15^\circ$.

z^*	Initial ($\alpha=15^\circ, \bullet =0$)	Optimized \bullet ($\bullet =0$)	Optimized \bullet & \bullet
0	44500 rpm	44500 rpm	46900 rpm
0.25	40600 rpm	45400 rpm	47000 rpm
0.5	37600 rpm	44500 rpm	45400 rpm
0.75	35000 rpm	43000 rpm	43900 rpm
1	32900 rpm	41400 rpm	41500 rpm
1.25	31000 rpm	39800 rpm	39900 rpm

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